

MECHANISMS OF THE FUTURE TECHNOLOGY TEACHER'S PREPARATION FOR PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITIES AIMED AT SOCIALIZING STUDENTS BASED ON A GENDER APPROACH

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Abstract: This article contains comments on theoretical approaches and mechanisms for preparing future technology teachers for pedagogical activities aimed at socializing students based on a gender approach.

Key words: pedagogical activity, mechanism, educational system, Technological education, gender approach, information.

Introduction:

Today, the process of active modernization of the capitalist world continues along with informatization, technologization, strengthening of nationalistic tendencies, violation of material and spiritual balance. *"The world has reached the limit of market-capitalist development,"* says A. I. Subbeto¹. The ongoing global civilizational changes throughout the world are contributing to the birth of new forms of organizing people's lives, changing the traditional world as a whole, disrupting its stability and stability. Since education is the main superstructure of society, it is responsible for the formation of a person, his spiritual image, moral development. Education, integrated with education from a socio-cultural point of view, is "a blessing of social importance... a purposeful process of education and learning for the benefit of the individual, family, society, and the state..."² considering that it is considered as Objective reality forces us to solve the issue of education, to remember what happened, what it is, what place social education will occupy in the context of control of the future society.

Without studying the terminological analysis of the concept of "social education", let's consider its meaning. M.A. Galaguzova determines that the uniqueness of social education is determined by the adjective "social"³. This means that social learning can be viewed from different perspectives. From the point of view of Academician A.V. Mudrik, social education includes the influence of society on a specific person or group of people. In this case, the society acts as a customer of social education implemented through various organizations and institutions. According to L.V. Mardakhayev, social education reflects a meaningful direction, its vector is aimed at preparing a person for the life of society⁴. At the same time, institutions of socialization (family, educational institutions, religious denominations, etc.), their values, meanings, and relationships are directly involved in the process of social education. According to our research, L.V. Mardakhayev's statement is important. "Education is education aimed at

¹ Суббетто, А. И. Социогенетика: системогенетика, общественный интеллект, образовательная генетика и мировое развитие. — М.: Логос. — 168 с.

² Закон РФ Об образовании // Официальные документы. Российская газета 21.12.2012. Ст. 52, с. 87. 2, с.

³ Галагузова, М. А. Социальная педагогика: Курс лекций / Под общей ред. М.А. Галагузовои. - М.: Гуманит. Изд. Центр ВЛАДОС, 2000. - 416с.

⁴ Мардахаев, Л. В. Педагогика среды: учебное пособие. — Новосибирск: Изд-во НГПУ, 2009. — 71 с.

creating conditions for the self-determination and socialization of the student, based on the socio-cultural, spiritual and moral values, rules and norms of behavior accepted in the society. is an activity organized in the system. individual, family, society, state".

Education in any society has certain goals determined by a certain historical period, national culture and state requirements (dominant ideology). Therefore, the question of forming a person who is able to live here and now, who is able to preserve and increase the wealth of society, and to contribute to its harmonious development, always arises. Accordingly, we not only help the individual (child, teenager, youth, adult and elderly) to enter the ever-changing society, teach him to feel "comfortable", but also constantly It is about forming a desire for self-development and self-improvement. Undoubtedly, it is necessary to develop socially important qualities that help a person change the world, make him kinder and more beautiful, nobler and wiser, moderately "feminine" and moderately "manly".

From this point of view, it is addressed to gender issues, education of young people based on gender approach, taking into account the interests of social-gender groups of the society and the demands of the new century.

For the effectiveness of the development of the social education system in higher education institutions of pedagogy, it is necessary to distinguish the theoretical and methodological approaches that are the foundation and basis of scientific research. For the completeness and reliability of the problem disclosure, it is fair to work with not one, but several approaches whose instructions complement each other.

Let's consider and analyze the concept of "approach". According to the Philosophical Dictionary, an "approach" is "a set of syntagmatic and pragmatic structures and mechanisms in knowledge and/or practice that characterize competing strategies and programs in philosophy, science, politics, or other fields⁵. It can be seen that this phenomenon reflects ongoing changes in the life structure of man and society in different periods of development, and it records qualitative changes in the forms of life activities. Analysis of the source base confirms the opinion that most authors are in a defined context. The problem approach follows the position that it reflects a formalized conceptualization of pedagogical reality and is defined by ideas, principles, and concepts. It defines, on the one hand, already established ideas that are being implemented in practice, and on the other hand, new, weakly expressed theoretical plans. As E.N. Stepanov and L.M. Luzina correctly stated: "*This is the direction of the teacher or the head of the educational institution in the implementation of his actions, the use of a certain set of concepts, ideas and methods of pedagogical activity is to encourage*".⁶ Arguing about this interpretation, we are not only about the application of forms, methods, methods, tools at the local level in the educational environment, but also about their implementation in order to effectively manage the pedagogical process, the success of which depends on the new trajectory of the educational movement - it depends on the individual a process that allows not only to adapt to the dynamically developing social space, but also to change it.

A slightly different interpretation from the position of the management aspect is offered by V. I. Zagvyazinsky, which is as follows: "*Management approaches are methods of analyzing the object of social management, assessing its state and the possibilities of change using*

⁵ Краткая философская энциклопедия. —М., 1994. —С. 349.

⁶ Степанов, Е. Н., Лузина, Л. М. Педагогу о современных подходах и концепциях воспитания. —М., 2002. —С. 83.

management tools."⁷. In this case, the "approach" is considered as a lever of production management, the main concepts of which are market, product, consumers, suppliers and producers.

Let's consider and analyze the approaches that are the basis of scientific research, that form the epistemological integrity of our problem, that force us to look differently at the processes of personality formation. Currently, the following approaches are clearly formed in local pedagogy and in the context of studying our problem: competence-based, axiological, philosophical-anthropological, systematic, cultural, synergetic. Let's dwell on the characteristics of each of them.

Thus, according to L.M. Mitina, "pedagogical competence" includes not only the knowledge component, but also the ways and means of implementing things accumulated in activities, communication and personal development (self-development). . In this interpretation, the author examines competence through the prism of professionalism and distinguishes two interacting substructures: activity and communication.

A slightly different message in defining the concept of "competence" was proposed by N. B. Shmeleva. In his opinion, competence is the connecting link that unites knowledge, the process of mastering and mastering social norms, values, as well as one's own profession, self-development and self-development is a component subject to specification. Arguing on this issue, we can say that the cultural component in this definition serves as a decisive factor in the teacher's educational activity. Yu. V. Senko follows the same position and emphasizes that professional competence can be considered from the prism of the teacher's integral characteristics. In this case, the latter shows the ability of the teacher, his level of professionalism and readiness to implement his professional plan. In addition, the humanistic component is an integral part of the teacher's activity, which refers to "dialogic communication, the desire to see the "other" in the student, socio-cultural reality. Analysis of studies conducted in Western Europe E. F. Zeer made it possible to present the competency-based approach as "*... priority orientation to educational goals - vectors: learning, self-determination, self-awareness, socialization and individual development.*"⁸ In this case, self-awareness is one of the components of professional education, which allows you to fill not only your own life, but also the lives of those around you with interesting, rich and meaningful life.

S.I. Grigoryev, a famous scientist of sociology, defined this problem as one of the important issues and stated that "*The set-based approach is directly related to the assessment of the quality of education, the formation of a set of competencies that a specialist should have, and the formation of professional activity.*"⁹ Developing this idea further, we can say that the author defines the scope of competence as a desired result of education, an indicator of the development and well-being of society.

⁷ Педагогический словарь: учебное пособие для студ. высш. учеб. заведений / В. И. Загвязинский, А. Ф. Закирова, Т. А. Строкова и др.; под ред. В. И. Загвязинского, А. Ф. Закировой.— М.: Изд. центр Академия, 2008. —352 с.

⁸ Зеер, Э. Ф. Психолого-педагогические конструкты качества профессионального образования // Образование и наука. 2002. №2 (14).

⁹ Григорьев, С. И. К вопросу о базовых критериях качества образования и ключевых компетенциях в современной России // Вестник учебно- методического объединения вузов России по образованию в области социальной работы.—2006. —№ 2. —С. 19-27.

The competency-based approach goes beyond the knowledge paradigm and expands the scope of the traditional approach to education. This approach includes not only a cognitive-knowledge component, but also a motivational, regulatory and moral component.

In accordance with the competency-based approach, the importance of the teaching team, and especially of each teacher, increases. A teacher's professional skills and self-education include not only the level of mastery of a certain subject, but also self-development, the formation of one's own views, independent study of the material and one's own - depends on the taste of self-education. Conducting dialogue and polylogue, establishing relations with the student audience, the development of individual subjectivity, the scope of thinking, the ability to use modern information flows, the culture of dialogic communication in various role situations, etc., including relations with members of the opposite sex. depends on the ability to install.

We note that along with the concept of "competence", basic (general cultural) competences, basic (professional) competences and special (profile-professional) competences are distinguished¹⁰. Let's give a brief description of each of them.

Basic (general cultural) competencies are the most general rules that reflect the level of manifestation of a person's social life in modern society. They are manifested in solving professional problems based on the implementation of informational, communication and socio-legal bases of personal behavior in civil society. Basic (professional) competences, in contrast to the main ones, reflect an unchanging field, specific characteristics of a certain professional activity (pedagogical, medical, engineering, etc.). Special (specialized-professional) competencies demonstrate specific characteristics of a certain subject or subject area of professional activity, which may include motivational, behavioral, cognitive, and other aspects.

The axiological approach is based on the philosophical theory of values, widespread in various fields of science, including pedagogy, in the 20th century. Supporters of the axiological approach emphasize that the world of values is objective, it is the socio-cultural reality itself, the life of man and society¹¹. In this case, it is necessary to clarify the ratio of social values, the subject of which is society, and personal values, which are manifested in the activity, behavior, and real social conditions of a particular person. On the one hand, individual, more precisely, personal values act as a form of existence of social values in the structure of a person. On the other hand, the degree of internalization of values is a reflection of what is offered by the social environment, the extent to which the subject is motivated to assimilate social values. Until the subject renews the importance of social values in the process of socialization, they remain external to the individual and cannot fully regulate his behavior. Learned values determine a person's position in society and serve as an important component of self-awareness. Analysis of the source base confirms that there are more than a hundred definitions of the concept of value with different analysis approaches. Scientists G. Golovny, I. S. Narsky emphasize the difference between value-goal and value-means.

¹⁰ Гришанова Н.А. Развитие компетентности специалиста как важнейшее направление реформирования профессионального образования. Десятый симпозиум. Квалиметрия в образовании: методология и практика/Под науч. ред. Н.А. Селезневаой и А.И. Субетто. Кн. 6. - М, 2002.

¹¹ Караковский, В. А., Новикова, Л. И., Селиванова, Н. Л. Воспитание? Воспитание... Воспитание: Теория и практика школьных воспитательных систем. —М.: Пед. общество России, 2000. —256 с.

However, such a difference is conditional, since the same value can act as a goal and a means. Many researchers believe that value can be understood as any object, including an ideal object that is very important to the subject. This means that the value corresponds to the basic needs of society, individual, social groups. Analyzing this phenomenon, we show that it is necessary to distinguish between the concepts of values and value orientations. The second determines the position of a person, his direction, including in the professional field, the field of vital interests. In other words, value orientations mean the component of the personality, attitude to material and spiritual values. Unlike values, value orientations refer to the personal meaning of various objects expressed in the mind and, accordingly, in human behavior¹².

It is distinguished by its own scale of values that reflects the national and cultural traditions of the Uzbek people, which is the best thing collected by previous generations. The essence of value cannot be understood in relation to culture. Analyzing the educational values that are the mechanism of regulating human behavior and activities, we emphasize that there are different approaches to their classification.

Continuing further analysis of the approaches in the system of social education of young people, we will focus on the philosophical and anthropological approach implemented in the practice of humanistic pedagogy. From this point of view, education is considered as a process aimed at developing individual abilities that are unique from birth. This development is based on the most important spiritual need of man - the need for education. The anthropological approach includes the education of a whole person, announcing the unity of the mental, emotional, moral, physical, and volitional aspects of development.

Today, the process of modernization of the educational system is carried out very transparently from the point of view of the ideas of the market economy, which, on the one hand, positively affects the quality component of people's lives, on the other hand, the violation of spiritual and material balance, ma the change of the concept of spiritual education, the loss of the highest value, its name is man.

Of course, it is necessary to modernize modern education, but on the basis of anthropocentrism as an expression of the humanistic paradigm of life, its inclusion in the complex system of informational, economic, technological, moral relations controlled by the attitude of a person to the world. Common virtues are the pursuit of truth, goodness, and beauty. This is a humanistic paradigm based on the understanding of a person as a part of nature, the value of his personality in education, the ability to change the trajectory of the development of society. Taking into account the educational function of education, we see, first of all, the manifestation of anthropocentrism in the most complex mechanisms of life development, in the realization of its potential in the socio-cultural space.

Thus, the above theoretical approaches offer new practical solutions in the implementation of youth education based on the gender approach. The more complex the changes taking place in the socio-cultural situation, the deeper the revision of previous theoretical concepts that determine new approaches to education should be.

¹² Бедерханова, В. П. Становление личностно-ориентированной позиции педагога: монография. —Краснодар, 2001. —220 с.

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